

ANALYSIS OF AGRO-INFORMATICS NEED AMONGST RICE FARMERS AMIDST INSECURITIES IN PLATEAU AND NASARAWA STATES, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The study analyzed agro-informatics needs amongst rice farmers amidst insecurities in Plateau and Nasarawa States, Nigeria. A multi-stage sampling technique was used to select 360 respondents for the study. Data were collected using questionnaires and the data collected were analyzed by employing both descriptive and inferential statistics. The results show that 74% of the respondents were male, while 75% were married. The mean household size of the farmers was 7. It further showed that 62.7% of the respondents had post-secondary education. The average age of the farmers was 41 years; the mean farming experience was 9 years, and the farmers had an average farm size of 3 hectares. The result of the logistic regression analysis revealed that educational qualification ($p = 0.01$), farm size ($p = 0.01$), and income ($p = 0.01$) all had significant influences on access to ICT by rice farmers in the study area. The study further revealed that “other farmers” (70%) were the major source of information among rice farmers in the study area. Also, the most available ICT tool among farmers in the study area was radio, as indicated by 70% of the respondents. However, the most required ICT tools among them were laptops (62.5%), mobile phones (61.9%), and digital cameras (60%). The findings further revealed that herdsmen attacks and kidnapping were the biggest insecurity challenges faced by the farmers. The regression result shows that educational level, farm size, farming experience, and income significantly influenced access to ICT. It was recommended that relevant government agencies should improve on security measures to safeguard the lives and properties of the farmers. This will provide an enabling environment for farmers to freely pursue their endeavours and improve their chances of accessing innovations such as information and communication technology.

Keywords: Agro-informatics, rice farmers, insecurities

INTRODUCTION

Agricultural informatics is the term for the applications and uses of information science and technology in various facets of agriculture (Channe, Kothari and Kadam, 2015). The major use of agricultural informatics is the use of information technology in agriculture. Agricultural informatics is interdisciplinary and may be

used in a variety of fields by utilizing various information technologies, including database technology, software technology, multimedia technology, web technology, networking technology, etc. (Rezník, Charvát, Lukas, Charvát Jr, Horáková and Kepka, 2015). According to Umar, Man, Nawi, Latif, and Samah (2017), information technology plays a

vital role in improving productivity in agriculture. The technology was seen as an important tool for agricultural production. Access to adequate and valuable knowledge by farmers will ultimately lead to improvement in their productivity (Hassan, Galadima, Man and Abu, 2019; Ramli, Man, Hassan, Bahaman, Omar, Sarina, Rahman and Ibrahim, 2019). Information and communication technologies have the potential to strengthen the ability of farmers to meet demands, provide an avenue for collective learning, disseminate time-sensitive information, such as changes in market prices or disease outbreaks, improve the effectiveness of agricultural and rural development programs, provide innovative ways of interaction between farmers and extension officers. (Bahrini and Qaffas, 2019).

The majority of Africans derive the majority of their nutritional energy from rice, therefore its production and use demand special consideration. In Nigeria, rice is a significant food and economic crop. According to Bello, Galadima, Anzaku and Allu (2014), rice serves multiple purposes, making a significant contribution to both domestic and international trade within the African sub-region as well as to national food security. According to Johnson, Takeshima, and Gyimah-Brempong (2013), Nigeria has a long history of domestic rice production and significant demand. Given the demand for rice across the nation and all socio-demographic categories, it is not surprising that it has become a significant staple food crop in Nigeria (Gyimah-Brempong, Johnson and Takeshima, 2016). However, insecurity, such as the Boko Haram insurgency, farmers/herdsmen clashes, banditry, communal conflicts, and other religious crises have engulfed Nigeria in the last few years, and have negatively affected the socio-economic development and stability of most parts of the country, especially the

Northern parts. People have had to flee from one settled area to another for security. This has seriously affected food crop production in Northern states such as Plateau and Nasarawa.

The broad objective of the study is to analyze the agro-informatics needs of rice farmers amidst insecurities in Plateau and Nasarawa States, Nigeria; while the specific objectives of the study are to:

- i. describe the socio-economic characteristics of rice farmers in the study areas.
- ii. ascertain the available ICT tools for rice farmers in the study areas.
- iii. find out the perceived effect of insecurity on the access to agricultural information in the study areas.
- iv. analyze the influence of socio-economic characteristics of rice farmers on access to information and communication technologies.

2.0 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Study Area

The study was conducted in Plateau and Nasarawa States, Nigeria. Both States are in the North Central zone of the country.

Plateau State has a total land area of 26 899 square kilometers and is located between longitude 8°22'N and 8°35'E and latitude 10°26'N and 10°40'E. The majority of the state is covered by the Northern Guinea savannah zone, which is characterized by small trees, grasses, and mosaic vegetation of the plateau type. Agricultural production activities are supported by the ecological and climatic features of the state (Olayemi, Idris, Ejima and Adeniyi, 2014).

Nasarawa State is bordered in the north by Kaduna State, in the west by the Federal Capital Territory (Abuja), in the south by the states of Kogi and Benue, and in the east by the states of Taraba and Plateau.

The State, which is located in the Southern Guinea Savanna zone of the nation, has a total land area of 28,735 square kilometers and a population of 2,679,433 (Idu, Fadiji and Evinemi, 2020). With a variety of cash crops produced throughout the year, agriculture serves as the foundation of the economy of Nasarawa State.

2.2 Population of the Study

The target population for this study was rice farmers in Plateau and Nasarawa States, Nigeria.

2.3 Sampling Technique

A multistage sampling technique was used to sample respondents for the study. The first stage involved the purposive selection of three (3) agricultural zones from each state. The selected zones include rice production areas in the states. For the second stage, three (3) blocks were chosen from each of the zones which resulted in eighteen (18) blocks. Two (2) cells were selected from each of the blocks which resulted in a total of thirty-six (36) cells. Finally, from each of the cells, ten (10) respondents were selected. The total number of respondents for the study was 360.

2.4 Data Collection and Analysis

Primary data were used for the study, and they were collected using a well-structured questionnaire, which was administered to smallholder rice farmers in the states with the assistance of local enumerators who are familiar with the states. Objectives of the study were achieved using descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentage, and mean, as well as logistic regression.

2.5 Model Specification

Logistic Regression

$$Y = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3 + b_4X_4 + b_5X_5 + \dots + b_{10}X_{10} + \mu$$

Where:

Y = access to information and communication technology tools (1 for Yes and 0 for no)

a = constant term

$b_1 - b_{10}$ = regression coefficients to be estimated

X_1 = age: (will be measured in years)

X_2 = gender; (male = 1, female = 0)

X_3 = education; (total number of years spent in formal education)

X_4 = marital status, (single = 1, married = 2, widowed = 3, divorced = 4)

X_5 = household size (measured by the number of people living under one roof)

X_6 = Farm size (measured in hectares)

X_7 = Farming experience (measured in years)

X_8 = Income (measured in Naira)

X_9 = Membership of association (yes = 1, otherwise = 0)

X_{10} = Access to extension services (number of extension contacts per cropping season)

μ = error TERM

3.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Socio-Economic Characteristics of Rice Farmers in the Study Area

Presented in Table 1 is the result of the socioeconomic characteristics of the rice farmers in the study area. The result revealed that most (74%) of the farmers were male while only 26% were female. This is in line with the findings of Idu *et al.* (2020), which stated that because men can engage in more physically demanding tasks, they are more involved in agricultural production than women. The result further revealed that 75% of the farmers were married, 19% were single, 3% of the respondents were divorced and the remaining 2% were widowed. This result aligns with the findings of Adetimehin, Okunlola, and Owolabi (2018) who found that most of the rice farmers in their study on the utilization of

agricultural information and knowledge were married. Agriculture is often family-centric, and farming activities are passed down through generations. In many cases, married individuals inherit or continue family farming traditions, contributing to a higher percentage of married farmers. Marriage often involves economic partnership and shared responsibilities. Married couples may jointly manage the household and the farm, pooling resources, labor, and skills. This economic collaboration can be advantageous for running a farm efficiently.

The household distribution of the respondents in Table 1 revealed that the majority (41.6%) of the respondents had between 4-6 persons living in their household, and 25.5% had a household size of 7-9. Also, 20.6% of them had a household size of more than 9 persons while only 16.6% of the respondents had a household size of 1-3. Meanwhile, the average household size of the respondents was 7. This implies that, on average, there are 7 individuals living in each household engaged in farming activities. This aligns with the findings of Ben-Chendo *et al.* (2014) who stated that the average size of farmers in the household was 8. A larger household size generally suggests a larger available labor force for agricultural activities (Giller, Delaune, Silva, Descheemaeker, van de Ven, Schut and van Ittersum, 2021). With seven individuals, more hands may be available to contribute to various tasks on the farm, such as planting, harvesting, and tending to livestock.

Table 1 further reveals the educational qualification of the rice farmers, and from the result, it was found that most (62.7%)

of them had post-secondary school education, 31.7% had secondary education, 4.5% had primary school education, and only 1.1% had no formal education. Farmers with higher educational qualifications are more likely to adopt modern and advanced farming practices. They may be better equipped to understand and implement innovative techniques, technologies, and sustainable agricultural methods. Higher education enhances critical thinking and problem-solving skills. Educated farmers are better positioned to make informed decisions regarding crop management, resource allocation, risk mitigation, and overall farm planning (Nwokoye, Oyim, Dimnwobi and Ekesiobi, 2019).

The age distribution of the farmers showed that the majority (30.3%) of them were between the ages of 31 and 40 years, 28.6% of the respondents were between the age of 41-50 years, 22.1% were older than 50 years, while 19.0% of the respondents were at most 30 years of age. The average age of the rice farmers was 41 years, which implies that most of the respondents are still within the productive active age and can effectively engage in farming activities. The finding is also in agreement with the assertions of Ben-Chendo *et al.* (2014) who found that the average age of rice farmers in their study was 44 years. The performance of a farmer is significantly influenced by age. Compared to the conservative old, younger individuals typically adapt to new technologies more quickly and successfully (Nwokoye *et al.*, 2019).

Most (60.8%) of the respondents had farming experience between 1 and 10 years, 33.7% of the respondents had

farming experience ranging from 11 to 20 years, while about 5.5% had at least 21 years of farming experience. The average year of farming experience is 9 years. Farmers with many years of farming experience will likely possess the ability to make sound decisions as regards resource allocation. Farming experience holds significant importance for farmers across various aspects of agricultural practices, decision-making, and overall sustainability. Farming experience allows farmers to develop practical skills related to crop cultivation, irrigation, pest control, and other essential aspects of agriculture (Nakano, Tsusaka, Aida and Pede, 2018). Through hands-on experience, farmers become adept at executing day-to-day tasks effectively.

The majority (57.5%) of the farmers had a

farm size of 1-3 hectares, 27.5% had a farm size of 4-6 hectares and 6.2% had more than 9 hectares of farmland. Also, 5.7% of the farmers had a farm size of 7-9 hectares while only 3.1% of them had a farm size of at most 1 hectare. The average farm size of rice farmers in the study area was 3 hectares. The average farm size of 3 hectares can provide insights into the potential productivity and yield of rice in the study area. Larger farm sizes may allow for economies of scale, enabling farmers to invest in machinery, technology, and efficient farming practices. Farm size is often correlated with the economic viability of agricultural operations (Ren, Liu, Van Grinsven, Reis, Jin, Liu and Gu, 2019). A farm size of 3 hectares may indicate a moderate scale of operation, where farmers can achieve a balance between efficiency and manageable input costs.

Table 1: Socio-economic characteristics of rice farmers

Variable	Freq	%
Gender		
Female	93	26
Male	259	74
Marital status		
Single	67	19
Married	261	75
Divorced	10	3
Widowed	8	2
Household size		
1 – 3	38	12.3
4 – 6	129	41.6
7- 9	79	25.5
> 9	64	20.6
<i>Mean</i>	7	
Educational level		
No formal school	4	1.1
Primary school	16	4.5
Secondary school	113	31.7
HSC/OND/NCE	115	32.3
BSc/HND	91	25.6
Postgraduate	17	4.8
Age		
= 30	67	19.0
31 -40	107	30.3
41 -50	101	28.6
> 50	78	22.1
<i>Mean</i>	41	
Experience		
= 10	211	60.8
11 -20	117	33.7
21 – 30	19	5.5
<i>Mean</i>	9	
Farm Size		
< 1	11	3.1
1-3	203	57.5
4-6	97	27.5
7-9	20	5.7
>9	22	6.2
<i>Mean</i>	3	

Source: Field survey, 2023

3.2 Information and Communication Tools Available to Farmers

Presented in Table 2 is the result of the information and communication tools available to farmers in the study area. From the result, it was revealed that radio was the most available ICT tool among rice farmers in the study area, as shown by 70% of the responses. In their study on analysis of communication and information communication technologies adoption in irrigated rice production, Nzonzo and Mogambi (2016) found that radios were the most used ICT tools by farmers. Radios are cost-effective, have low power consumption, have widespread availability, and are easy to operate. The affordability, simplicity, portability, and cultural significance of radios make them a popular and effective communication tool for rural farmers. Radios play a crucial role in providing agricultural information, fostering community connectivity, and supporting the diverse needs of rural

populations (Fidelugwuowo, 2021). The second most available ICT tool among rice farmers in the study area is the mobile phone as indicated by 68.6% of the farmers. The increasing prevalence of mobile phone access among rural farmers can be attributed to the reduction in the cost of purchasing them, improved infrastructure, agricultural extension services, social connectivity, and government initiatives, all of which have contributed to the widespread adoption of this technology in rural areas (Sanusi, Petu-Ibikunle and Mshelia, 2021).

The result further shows that 53.3%, 43.1%, and 41.9% of rice farmers in the study area had access to television, WhatsApp, and Facebook respectively. Other ICT tools available to the farmers include Internet (35.8%), email (20.8%), Instagram (14.4%), and Twitter (12.2%). The least available ICT tool in the study area is a digital camera, as shown by 8.1% of the responses.

Table 2: Information and Communication Tools Available to Farmers

Information and Communication Tools	Frequency	Percentage
Radio	252	70.0
Television	192	53.3
Mobile phone	247	68.6
Flash drives	32	8.9
CDs/DVDs	35	9.7
Internet	129	35.8
Laptops	60	17.6
Desktop computers	42	11.7
Digital cameras	29	8.1
WhatsApp	155	43.1
Instagram	52	14.4
Facebook	151	41.9
Email	75	20.8
Twitter	44	12.2

Source: Field survey, 2023

3.3 Insecurity Challenges Faced by Rice Farmers in the Study Area

The result in Table 3 shows the insecurity challenges faced by rice farmers in the study area. The mean score of responses shows that the biggest insecurity challenge faced by the farmers is the herdsmen attack with a mean score of 3.18. This is in line with the findings of Mohammed and Baba (2018) who stated that herdsmen-farmer clashes have constituted a significant barrier to food security in the country. Herdsmen attacks have resulted in the loss of lives among rice farmers. Additionally, these attacks often lead to the destruction of crops, farmlands, and agricultural infrastructure, causing a direct impact on the livelihoods of rice farmers. The insecurity caused by herdsmen attacks forces many rice farmers to abandon their farms and homes, leading to internal displacement. This displacement disrupts communities and exacerbates social and economic challenges, as farmers may lose access to their primary source of income and face difficulties resettling (Erondu and Nwakanma, 2018). The destruction of farmlands and crops contributes to food insecurity in the affected regions. Rice is a staple food in Nigeria, and attacks on rice farms can have severe consequences for

local and national food supply, leading to increased prices and decreased availability.

The result further shows that kidnapping is also a major insecurity challenge faced by the farmers, as shown by a mean score of 3.00. The most immediate and direct impact of kidnapping is on the physical safety and well-being of rice farmers. Kidnappings create an atmosphere of fear and insecurity, making it challenging for farmers to carry out their daily activities, including tending to their crops. Pervasive kidnapping incidents may lead to the displacement of rice farmers. Fearing for their safety, farmers may be forced to abandon their farmlands and migrate to safer areas, disrupting agricultural activities and potentially contributing to food insecurity (Juochi and Asiegwu, 2023). The farmers also identified religious crisis, banditry, and robbery as the other forms of insecurity that affect their productivity. Ongoing insecurity may raise concerns about the long-term sustainability of rice farming in affected regions. If security challenges persist, there is a risk of a decline in agricultural activities, leading to food insecurity and economic instability.

Table 3: Insecurity Challenges Faced by Rice Farmers in the Study Area

Insecurity	Mean Score
Banditry	2.67
Robbery	2.51
Herdsmen attack	3.18
Kidnapping	3.00
Religious clashes	2.19

Source: Field survey, 2023

3.4 Socio-Economic Factors that Influence Access to Information and Communication Technologies by Rice Farmers in the Study Area

Table 4 shows the result of the logistic regression analysis on the effect of socio-economic factors on access to information and communication technologies by rice farmers in the study area. The Cox and Snell R^2 is a measure of how well the independent variables in the model explain the variation in the dependent variable. In this case, the value of 0.581 indicates that approximately 58.1% of the variations in access to ICT by rice farmers can be predicted by the socio-economic factors included in the model. This is a moderately strong explanatory power, suggesting that the model captures a

significant portion of the variability in ICT access. The remaining 41.9% of the variations not explained by the model could be attributed to unobserved variables, measurement errors, or other factors that were not included in the analysis. It's essential to recognize and acknowledge that there are aspects influencing ICT access that are not considered in the current model. The result highlights that educational level; farm size, and income are identified as significant variables influencing access to ICT. The term "significant" in this context means that changes in these variables are associated with a statistically significant impact on the likelihood of farmers having access to ICT.

Table 4: Result of Logistic Regression Analysis of Socio-Economic Factors on Access to ICT Tools by Rice Farmers

	B	Std. Error	Wald	
Gender	.406	.425	.909	.340
Marital Status	-.352	.385	.835	.361
HHS	.192	.124	2.396	.122
Age	.015	.027	.316	.574
Education Level	.500	.085	34.242	.000*
Farm size	5.200	1.190	19.097	.000*
Farming Experience	.483	.284	2.886	.089
Income	.001	.10	15.381	.000*
Constant	4.550	1.812	6.306	.012

Cox and Snell R squared = 0.581

Source: Field survey, 2023

*significant at 1% probability

The regression result reveals that educational qualification (.000) was positive and significant at a 1% probability. Hence, for a unit increase in educational qualification, if every other variable is constant, there will be increased access to information and communication technologies by rice farmers in the study

area. This result agrees with the findings of Ali (2012) which stated that the level of education of farmers significantly influences their adoption of ICT for farming decisions. This implies that higher educational levels may be associated with a greater likelihood of having access to ICT, as individuals with more education

often possess the skills and awareness to utilize technology effectively (Paltasingh and Goyari, 2018). The finding underscores the importance of educational qualification in explaining variations in the dependent variable. In the context of the study or analysis, it could mean that individuals with higher educational qualifications may exhibit certain behaviors, characteristics, or outcomes that are captured by the dependent variable.

The result in Table 2 showed that farm size (.000) was positive and significant at a 1% probability. The result shows that an increase in farm size, assuming all other variables remain constant, will lead to an increase in access to ICT by rice farmers. This aligns with the assertions of Achichi *et al.* (2023) who found that farm size significantly influenced farmers' access to agricultural information. Larger farm sizes may indicate greater economic capacity and access to resources. Farmers with larger operations may have more financial means to invest in ICT infrastructure, such as computers, smartphones, and internet connectivity, enhancing their access to technology. Larger farms may benefit from economies of scale, which can extend to the adoption of technology. The cost per unit of ICT infrastructure may be lower for larger farms, making it more economically feasible for them to invest in and maintain these technologies. Larger farms may require more sophisticated management practices, and ICT tools can contribute to increased efficiency in managing larger-scale agricultural operations (Krell, Giroux, Guido, Hannah, Lopus, Caylor and Evans, 2021). This may include precision farming techniques, data-driven decision-making, and other technology-enabled practices.

Income (.000) was significant at 1% and

had a positive relationship with access to ICT. This implies that for a unit increase in income, there will be a 0.001 increase in their access to ICT. This is in line with Nwokoye *et al.* (2019) who found that income is a major socio-economic determinant of rice farmers' adoption of ICT. Higher income levels may facilitate the ability to afford and invest in ICT infrastructure and services. Higher-income levels often enable farmers to afford and invest in ICT infrastructure, devices, and services. Wealthier farmers may have the financial capacity to purchase smartphones, computers, or other technological tools, as well as access the internet and relevant software applications. The positive relationship suggests that, as farmers experience an increase in income, they are more likely to adopt and utilize ICT tools and services (Abegunde, Sibanda and Obi, 2019). This may include using technology for farm management, accessing market information, or employing precision agriculture practices. Access to ICT tools can contribute to increased productivity and efficiency in farming practices. Wealthier farmers with greater access to technology may benefit from real-time information, weather forecasts, and other digital resources that aid decision-making and improve agricultural outcomes.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study underscores the critical importance of leveraging agro-informatics to bolster resilience and promote sustainability within the sector. By analyzing and synthesizing relevant data, the research provides valuable insights into the specific needs, challenges, and opportunities rice farmers face at the intersection of agriculture and technology. It demonstrates that agro-informatics tools, such as mobile applications, digital platforms, and localized information

systems, can offer practical solutions for enhancing decision-making, improving resource management, and mitigating insecurity impacts.

The following recommendations were made:

- i. Relevant government agencies should improve existing security measures to safeguard farmers' lives and properties. This will provide an enabling environment for farmers to freely pursue their endeavors and improve their chances of

accessing innovations such as information and communication technology.

- ii. Various stakeholders should prioritize rural infrastructure, including reliable electricity and internet connectivity. Improving infrastructure is foundational for the successful implementation of agro-informatics solutions and ensures that farmers have access to essential resources.
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